

Callistoctopus furvus

Structural elements, components and skin patterns

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Distinguishing Characteristics:

1. Long, slender arms; front arms are thickest and longest, L2 and R2 are second largest, rear four arms are smallest
2. Strictly nocturnal (not seen outside of den between sunrise and sunset)
3. Brick red is incorporated into almost every skin pattern, black is not present, and it has regularly spaced rows of permanent white spots along the entire body that are always at least partially visible on the arms
4. The deimatic pattern consists of large polka dots over the entire body
5. Many mantle papillae take the form of elongated longitudinal ridges or U-shaped flaps when fully expressed
6. Six distinct mantle shapes
7. Small arm web (extends only one quarter to one third the length of the arms)
8. Only occasionally executes a parachute attack
9. Buries in soft substrate or retreats into holes in soft or hard substrate

1. Long, slender arms; front arms are thickest and longest, L2 and R2 are second largest, rear four arms are smallest

3. Brick red is incorporated into almost every skin pattern, black is not present, and it has regularly spaced rows of permanent white spots along the entire body that are always at least partially visible on the arms

The three colors displayed by *C. furvus*, brick red (a), which can appear in darker or lighter shades as seen in the upper inset (b); white (c); and stippled, which, depending on the body part and light source, can appear bluish (d), orangish (e) or greenish (f).

Unlike other co-occurring species of octopus, *C. furvus* has rows of white spots that cover the entire body when fully (a) or partially (b) expressed. Even when the rest of the body is brick red (c), faint white spots are always visible on the arms.

4. Deimatic skin pattern consists of large polka dots over the entire body

HB Oct 28 2022 large

5. Many mantle papillae take the form of elongated longitudinal ridges or U-shaped flaps when fully expressed

<p>Smooth (19.85%) (papillae not expressed at all)</p>	
<p>Coarse (19.98%) (papillae partially expressed)</p>	
<p>Papillate (54.90%) (papillae fully expressed)</p>	

Figure 10. Skin textures observed in *C. furvus*. Percentages indicate the proportion of time each texture was displayed in three hrs of video (5.27% of the time texture was unknown). Terminology derived from Hanlon and Wolterding, 1989.

Comparison of the U-shaped mantle papillae of *C. furvus* (a and b) with the smaller and pointier papillae of co-occurring *Octopus briareus* (c) and the similar-looking papillae of co-occurring *O. insularis* (d).

6. Six Mantle Shapes

Elongated—mantle is completely deflated, narrow and linearly elongated (a); Torpedo—mantle is deflated and elongate, often shown while jetting (b); Ogive—mantle is partly inflated, especially ventrally, partially (c) to nearly fully inflated (d), and appearing elongated with a pronounced posterior mantle tip (P & S, 1971); Rugby ball—moderately inflated mantle with no elongated tip (e); Bulbous—mantle is completely inflated and round (f).

7. Small arm web (extends only one quarter to one third the length of the arms)

Comparison of the relatively small arm web of *C. furvus* (a and b) with *Octopus briareus* (c) and *O. insularis* (d), both of which co-occur with *C. furvus* in the Turks and Caicos Islands. In each of these photos, the individual's arm web is fully extended in either a parachute attack (a and c) or deimatic display (b and d).

9. Buries in soft substrate

Timelapse sequence of *C. furvus* burying itself in loose sediment. Filming commenced a few seconds after the initiation of burying and proceeded for another 02:33. Initially, the octopus used its arms and web to displace a rock (00:12) in order to access the loose sediment beneath (a-c). It then spent the next 02:07 moving its arms within the substrate, presumably digging (d), before rapidly (<3 sec) pulling its head and mantle into the substrate (e-g). See Supplementary video #8 for full sequence.

9. Disappears completely into holes generally in soft substrate

Timelapse sequence of *C. furvus* entering an existing hole in the substrate. The sequence from first arm contact with the hole to complete disappearance within it was 01:40. Upon situating itself over the hole (a), the octopus spent the next 01:30 putting each of its arms inside the hole and occasionally inflating and deflating its mantle, resulting in the dislodgement of loose sediment (b). Once the majority of its arms were inside the hole (c), its disappearance (d-g) proceeded rapidly (>10 sec), as it presumably used its arms to pull its head and mantle inside. See Supplementary video #7 for full sequence.

BODY REGIONS (regions of body that can differ in pattern, color or texture from adjacent body regions):

I. Mantle

II. Siphon

III. Head

IV. Arm bases

V. Arms and web

VI. Eye bulbs

VII. Eye

VIII. Ventral arm area

Chromatic Components

For each body region

CHROMATIC COMPONENTS by BODY REGION:

I. Mantle

- a.) Brick red
- b.) Rows of white spots
- c.) Stippled
- d.) Brick red blotches
- e.) White blotches
- f.) Central white stripe
- g.) Two central white mantle blotches

II. Siphon

- a.) Brick red
- b.) White

III. Head

- a.) Brick red
- b.) Rows of white spots
- c.) White
- d.) Stippled
- e.) Brick red blotches
- f.) White blotches
- g.) Central white stripe
- h.) White head bar

IV. Arm bases

- a.) Brick red
- b.) Rows of white spots
- c.) Stippled
- d.) Brick red blotches
- e.) White blotches
- f.) Central white stripe
- g.) Large central white arm base blotch

V. Arms and web

- a.) Brick red
- b.) Rows of white spots
- c.) Stippled
- d.) Brick red arm bars
- e.) White arm bars
- f.) Brick red front four arms, white back four arms

VI. Eye bulbs

- a.) Brick red
- b.) Rows of white spots
- c.) White
- d.) Stippled
- e.) Brick red blotches
- f.) White blotches
- g.) Central white stripe
- h.) White head bar
- i.) Brick red eye bar

VII. Eye

- a.) Brick red
- b.) White
- c.) Upper half brick red/lower half white
- d.) White pupil margin
- e.) Pupil dilation

VIII. Ventral arm area

- a.) Brick red
- b.) White

IX. Papillae

- a.) Smooth
- b.) Coarse
- c.) Papillate

I. Mantle

a) Brick red (with subdued white spots on right)

faint

moderate

prominent

b) Rows of white spots

I. Mantle

c) Stippled (a mixture of white points interspersed with brick red veining creating an intermediate color)

Sparse

Intense

d) Brick red blotches

I. Mantle

e) White blotches

f) Central white stripe

I. Mantle

Faint

Intense

g) Two central white blotches

II. Siphon

a) Brick red

b) White

III. Head

a) brick red

faint

moderate

intense

b) Row of white spots

III. Head

c) White

d.) Stippled (a mixture of white interspersed with brick red veining creating an intermediate color)

III. Head

Sparse

Intense

e) Brick red blotches

f) White blotches

III. Head

g) Central white stripe

Present

Absent

h) White head bar

Brick red eyebrow Pulse (A dynamic component)

IV. Arm bases

a) Brick red

faint

moderate

b) Rows of white spots

prominent

IV. Arm bases

c) Stippled (a mixture of white points interspersed with brick red veining creating an intermediate color)

sparse

intense

d) Brick red blotches

IV. Arm bases

e) White blotches

f) Central white stripe

IV. Arm bases

f) Large central white arm base blotch

V. Arms and web

a) Brick red

faint

moderate

prominent

b) Rows of white spots

V. Arms and web

c) Stippled (a mixture of white points interspersed with brick red veining creating an intermediate color)

d) Brick red arm bars

V. Arms and web

e) White arm bars

f) Brick red front four arms, white back four arms

VI. Eye Bulbs

a) Brick red

b) Rows of white spots

VI. Eye Bulbs

c) White

d) Stippled

VI. Eye Bulbs

sparse

intense

e) Brick red blotches

VI. Eye Bulbs

f) White blotches

g) Central white stripe

VI. Eye Bulbs

Present

Absent

h) White head bar

i) Brick red eye bar

VII. Eye

a) Brick red

b) White

c) Upper half brick red/lower half white

VII. Eye

Present

Absent

d) White pupil margin

Slit

Rectangle

Wide

e) Pupil dilation

VIII. Ventral arm area

Brick red

White

Skin patterns

SKIN PATTERNS:

1. Brick Red
 - a) Brick Red
 - b) Brick Red with Central White Arm Base Blotch
 - c) Brick Red with Three Central White Mantle and Arm Base Blotches
 - d) Brick Red with Three Central White Mantle and Arm Base Blotches and White Arm Bars
 - e) Brick Red with Three Central White Mantle and Arm Bases Blotches and White and Brick Red Arm Bars
2. Racing Stripe
 - a) Racing Stripe with Brick Red Front Four Arms
 - b) Racing Stripe with White Arms
3. Mostly White
 - a) Mostly White with Sparse Brick Red Mantle and Arm Base Blotches and Brick Red Arm Bars
 - b) Mostly White with Intense Brick Red Mantle and Arm Base Blotches and Brick Red Arm Bars
4. Mottle
 - a) Sparse mottle
 - b) Intense mottle
5. Stippled
 - a) Stippled
 - b) Stippled with Rows of White Spots
 - c) Stippled with Rows of White Spots and Brick Red Blotches on Arm Bases
6. Polka Dotted
 - a) Polka Dotted
 - b) Polka Dotted with Brick Red Blotches on Mantle and Arm Bases

1a) Brick Red

Regatta Mar 13 2022 1st

Shark Alley Dec 2 2021 1st

Regatta Mar 13 2022, 1st individual

June 30 2020, 1st individual

June 14 2023 Regatta

June 26 2022 Regatta

HDL Apr 27, 1st individual

HB July 28 2020

Apr 29 2022 Fish Rock

SZ May 3 2023

Oct 26 2022 SZ 1st

1b) Brick Red with Central White Arm Base Blotch

1c) Brick Red with Three Central White Mantle and Arm Base Blotches

July 28, 2020

Cox Hotel Nov 24 3rd

HB Aug 2 2020

March 26, 2022 R

Regatta Sept 3 2022 medium

1d) Brick Red with Three Central White Mantle and Arm Base Blotches and White Arm Bars

1d) Brick Red with Three Central White Mantle and Arm Base Blotches and White Arm Bars

1e) Brick Red with Three Central White Mantle and Arm Bases Blotches and White and Brick Red Arm Bars

2a) Racing Stripe with Brick Red Front Four Arms

Sept 8, 2021 HB

July 28, 2020

HB Feb 27 2023

July 10, 2022 R 2nd

July 4 2022 Admiral's

May 8, 2022 Regatta 1st individ

2. a) Racing Stripe with White Arms

3a) Mostly White with Sparse Brick Red Mantle and Arm Base Blotches and Brick Red Arm Bars

* Distinguished from mottle by angularity and large size of white shapes

3b) Mostly White with Intense Brick Red Mantle and Arm Base Blotches and Brick Red Arm Bars

* Distinguished from mottle by angularity and large size of white shapes

4a) Mottle (sparse) (<25%)

Aug 3, 2023 regatta

SZ Feb 25 2022

Regatta Mar 13 2nd individ

SZ Apr 4 2022 3rd individ

HB Aug 6 2020

4b) Mottle (intense) (>25%)

5a) Stippled

5b) Stippled with moderate white spots

Sept 1 2022 Regatta

Cox_Hotel_Nov_24 2021 3rd

Oct 27, 2022 HB

Oct 28 HB large

HB Sept 8 2021

Aug 26 2020 HB

June 30 2020 HB 1st

5b) Stippled with Rows of White Spots

5c) Stippled with Rows of White Spots on and Brick Red Blotches on Arm Bases

6a) Polka Dotted

Sept 8, 2021 HB

HB Oct 28 2022 small

SZ Oct 26 2022 2nd

HB Oct 28 2022 large

July 4, 2022 Admiral's

June 30 2020

Shark Alley Dec 2, 2021

Sept 1, 2022 R

Mar 13 2022 regatta 1st

Regatta Mar 13 2022 2nd

Regatta July 10 2022

6b) Polka Dotted with Brick Red Blotches on Mantle and Arm Bases

Unilateral patterns

Observed in only one instance

Skin patterns observed only on one occasion in a single individual of *Callistoctopus furvus* in videos and photographs recorded in the vicinity of South Caicos. In a) the mantle, head and arm bases are Brick red along with the distal two thirds of the arms, while the upper arms are White. The skin pattern in b) closely resembles Racing Stripe except that all arms are Brick red and the racing stripe is highly subdued, appearing a paler shade of Brick red than the surrounding areas rather than White. In c), a small individual's distal two thirds of the mantle (delineated by a diagonal border) appeared stippled, while the rest of the body displayed Brick Red with Central White Arm Base Blotch. The skin pattern in d) resembles the fully expressed Polka Dotted pattern, except that the Rows of white spots do not appear in the middle two thirds of the mantle (they do appear in a small region of the mantle near the head and on the mantle tip). This final pattern was also observed in a photograph from St. Thomas USVI, see "Media sourced from other geographic locations" and Supplementary Photo #1.

Textures

Papillae

Large papillae

Small papillae

Skin Texture

Smooth

Coarse (Moderately expressed papillae)

Papillate

Postures

- 1) Deimatic Arm Spread
- 2) Elongated
- 3) Flamboyant
- 4) Flattened
- 5) Flower Pose
- 6) Momentum Posture
- 7) Gnome
- 8) Parachute
- 9) Spread Arms
- 10) Torpedo

1) Deimatic Arm Spread

Bulbous or ogive mantle at roughly right angles to head and arm bases. Arms curled horizontally and spread widely, with arm web fully extended.

2) Elongated

*only observed once (May 8 regatta 1st)

Mantle in line with head and arms, arms taper to a tight point. Octopus utilizes small puffs of jet propulsion.

3) Flamboyant Display

Ogive mantle at right angle to head and arm bases. First arm pair held aloft in a corkscrew shape while other arms trail behind or locomote. Often occurs in conjunction with bipedal locomotion.

4) Flattened

*Only two recorded instances (Aug 2 2020 Sept 8 2021 HB)

Entire body held flat against the substrate. Arms spread and curled horizontally.

5) Flower Pose

Mantle at a 45-90° angle to head and arm bases, either in the water column or touching the substrate. Head lifted above the rest of the body and arms curled close around arm bases on the substrate.

6) Momentum Posture

Mantle is roughly perpendicular to arm bases and arms trail behind usually in bundles of four on either side. Octopus moves across substrate using arms and brief jet propulsion.

7) Gnome

Ogive mantle held at a roughly 150° angle. Arms curled upwards.

8) Parachute

Mantle is roughly perpendicular to arm bases. Arms are spread and envelop and object with arm web fully extended.

9) Spread Arms

Mantle at approximate right angle to head and arm bases, arms spread roughly evenly around body with arms fully or mostly extended.

10) Torpedo

Mantle is torpedo shaped, and in line with head and arms. Octopus utilizes jet propulsion with arms trailing loosely behind.

Summary Table of Behaviors

Behaviour	Description
Arm Exploration (21.82%)	Octopus uses arms to search crevices, with the rest of the body mostly stationary
Attempted Arm Capture (0.31%)	Octopus “throws” out one or more arms in the direction of prey in an attempt to capture it
Bipedal Locomotion (0.80%)	Octopus moves across substrate on two back arms, usually while raising front two a up in a corkscrew shape (see O’Brien and O’Brien, 2022)
Burying (6.24%)	Octopus uses funnel and/or arms to bury itself in the sand
Crawling (41.29%)	Octopus uses arms to move across the substrate
Entering Hole (3.41%)	Octopus squeezes into an existing hole in the substrate, presumably using its arms and suckers to pull its body inside
Grooming*	Octopus rubs its arms all over its body in a writhing motion, including inside the funnel and mantle cavity (“cleaning maneuver” of Packard and Sanders, 1971)
Jetting (4.79%)	Octopus shoots water from funnel to rapidly move away
Parachute Attack (0.65%)	Octopus engulfs a rock, coral head or prey with its arms and web
Prey Handling (0.85%)	Octopus handles and/or subdues prey
Stationary (17.41%)	Octopus remains in one location, with its only motion being ventilation or small arm movements